

D6.2

Transformation toolbox & ingest and processing workflow

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1. List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation or acronym	Meaning
ACDH-CH	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage
API	Application Programming Interface
ATR	Automated Text Recognition
CCLS	(Annual) Conference of Computational Literary Studies
CIDOC CRM	Comité international pour la documentation Conceptual Reference Model
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CLS	Computational Literary Studies
CLS INFRA	Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (project)
CLSCor	Core ontology developed in the CLS INFRA project for CLS corpora
D (e.g., D6.1, D5.1)	Deliverable
DSL	Domain Specific Language
DTA	Deutsches Textarchiv
DraCor	Drama Corpora Project
FRBRoo	Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records object oriented
JCLS	Journal of Computational Literary Studies
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LLMs	Large Language Models
LOD	Linked Open Data
LRMoo	Library Reference Model object oriented
M (e.g., M24)	Month
ML	Machine Learning
NER	Named Entity Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OAuth 2.0	Open Authorization 2.0
OIDC	Open ID Connect
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PID	Persistent Identifier
PoS	Part of Speech
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
SARI	Swiss Art Research Infrastructure project
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organisation System
SSH Open Marketplace	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace
TCF	Text Corpus Format
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative

TEITOK	a Tokenized TEI environment
TTL	Terse RDF Triple Language
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VELD	Versioned Executable Logic and Data
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

2. Publishable summary

This deliverable describes the work in task 6.2 of the CLS INFRA project, with the goal to combat the heterogeneity and incoherence of the CLS ecosystem and to improve the interoperability between data and tools, through a special toolkit, the Transformation Toolbox, providing harmonised means for converting data between formats.

To this end, a novel technical concept has been proposed, VELD (Versioned Executable Logic and Data) – a generic mechanism to harmonise description of and improve interoperability between heterogeneous resources and to construct processing pipelines combining heterogeneous tools using widely adopted technologies, which at the same time ensures reproducibility of the workflows. This mechanism was complemented with a comprehensive overview of resources, tools and data, available in the domain using a common unifying data model.

Taken together these results represent a significant contribution to the consolidation of the CLS ecosystem.

3. Introduction and methodology

The CLS INFRA project set out to develop an infrastructure for the CLS community to enable sustainable and open scholarship in this emerging field. Although there are clear signs that this community is forming and thriving ([JCLS](#), [CCLS](#)), the technical ecosystem is still rather nascent and as such is faced with some major challenges. As detailed in D7.1¹, these can be summarised under the keywords: *dispersion, heterogeneity and instability*. Whilst more and more resources are being created in the context of numerous projects, there is little overarching cohesion, yielding heterogeneous resources, deployed through diverse channels, often in incompatible ways. Moreover, the way in which computational processing is applied is ad-hoc and not standardised, hampering the reproducibility of produced results.

As proposed in D7.1, to tackle these endemic problems, inherent to any emerging field, two lines of action need to be pursued: a) standardisation and normalisation of resource descriptions and processes by formulating common taxonomies and controlled vocabularies, b) construction and provision of technical infrastructure enabling interoperability between existing systems and supporting execution of automated processing tasks.

In close collaboration with WPs 3, 5, 7, and 8, WP6 has contributed to both these aspects:

The main proposition and central goal of WP6 was to develop a conceptual model to harmonise and formalise the description of the objects of discourse. Starting from what is considered the central epistemic object in CLS, the corpus, it must be able to express information not only about the data resources (corpora and their constituent documents) but also about the tools² used to process –

¹ Börner, I., & Trilcke, P. (2023). CLS INFRA D7.1 On Programmable Corpora (v1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7664964>

² Through this document we use the term "tool" as catch-all short-hand for all kinds of software, scripts, applications, as well as services that can be used to process data, deliberately not distinguishing between software code that needs to be executed by the user and an online application that can be used remotely.

enrich, transform, analyse – these data objects. Such a model has been formalised as the [CLSCor ontology](#), with its initial version introduced in D6.1³. Given the lack of community-wide agreement on the terminology, the development of the model was based mainly on empirical material, that is the information encountered to describe available literary corpora and auxiliary resources. A certain degree of harmonisation and formalisation of this mostly idiosyncratic, verbose, unstructured information, manifested in the CLSCor ontology and the [CLSCor catalogue](#) represents a major outcome of this task.

As regards the construction of the technical infrastructure:

Given the wide variety of methodological approaches and technical setups employed by the CLS community, one cannot assume a clear and fixed set of user requirements to inform the design and development of the infrastructure. Rather, a prototyping approach was required, to serve as a "learning vehicle" – to find out what is really needed by the community, in an iterative, co-creative process, based on practical use cases and in collaboration with the scholars (cf. details on this prototyping approach in D7.1). Moreover, the highly distributed and heterogeneous nature of the ecosystem with a multitude of existing tools offered by different providers implies a distributed nature of the developed infrastructure.

Various aspects of constructing such a technical infrastructure for CLS have been addressed in multiple tasks across the project: WP7 focused on the development and provision of standardised APIs, implementing the concept of "Programmable Corpora"^{4,5}. WP8 has inventoried (D8.1⁶ and D8.2⁷) and further developed the many existing tools available for Natural Language Processing (NLP) and other tasks, while WP3 provided a baseline methodological user needs analysis (D3.1⁸) and a survey on CLS

³ Ďurčo, M., Charvat, V. M., Börner, I., Mrugalski, M., & Odebrecht, C. (2022). CLS INFRA D6.1 Inventory of existing data sources and formats. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7520287> - D6.1 delivered an overview of the data landscape, an inventory of existing data sources, as well as the initial concept of the transformation matrix and the first version of the CLSCor data model.

⁴ Börner, I., & Trilcke, P. (2024). CLS INFRA D7.3 On Versioning Living and Programmable Corpora (v1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11081934>

⁵ Boerner, I., Trilcke, P., Milling, C., Fischer, F., & Sluyter-Gäthje, H. (2023, Juli 12). Dockerizing DraCor – A Container-based Approach to Reproducibility in Computational Literary Studies [Slides]. DH2023, Graz, Austria. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8183676>

⁶ Cinková, S., Birkholz, J. M., Börner, I., Dejaeghere, T., Heiden, S., Janssen, M., Křen, M., Pozo, A. P., & Ros, S. (2024). CLS INFRA D8.1 Report of the tools for the basic Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks in the CLS context. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14294801> - D8.1 offers a comprehensive overview of tools for wide variety of tasks developed and/or provided by project partners

⁷ Birkholz, J., Salvador, R., Cinková, S., Decorde, M., Fernandez, V. D. F., Heiden, S., Janssen, M., Křen, M., & Pozo, A. P. (2024). CLS INFRA D8.2 Report & prototypes for annotation as enrichment. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11094000>

⁸ Christof Schöch, Evgeniia Fileva, & Julia Dudar. (2022). CLS INFRA D3.1 Baseline Methodological User Needs Analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6389333>

methods (D3.2⁹). Additionally, D6.3¹⁰ delivered a comprehensive overview of formats for encoding textual data used both in the domain of computational literary studies and of computational linguistics, as well as a refined concept of the transformation matrix to serve as conceptual framework for the implementation of a toolkit.

Building on these foundations, the contribution of task 6.2 was to deliver a special toolkit, the so-called *Transformation Toolbox*, to facilitate the comparability and integration among corpora and to improve the interoperability between corpus data and tools through format conversions.

Conceptually, the Transformation Toolbox consists of three parts:

- a) Tooling – actual software or services to process and transform data
- b) Interoperability mechanism to harmonise the use of heterogeneous tools and data
- c) Registry of available tools and data capturing information about their technical characteristics

Given the rich offer of existing tools¹¹, the focus of the task was not on developing new tools but rather on the interoperability mechanism allowing to harmonise and simplify the use of the existing tools.

While the basic approach to ensuring interoperability would be to transform data into the formats required by individual tools, or to adapt individual tools to accept data in different formats, task 6.2 proposes a much more general mechanism for harmonising the use of heterogeneous tools: The *VELD* (Versioned Executable Logic and Data) concept – detailed in section "[5.3 VELD - Versioned Executable Logic and Data](#)" – introduces a generic wrapper for data and executable code, employing the widely used technologies [Git](#) and [Docker](#), which allows to define complex processing chains consisting of multiple steps, while ensuring their reproducibility and repeatability¹². This approach is applicable not only to format conversions, but to all kinds of processing tasks, including NLP annotations (tokenisation, lemmatisation, Part of Speech - PoS, Named Entity Recognition - NER) and various kinds of analysis (structure, semantics, style, etc.), or even for computing statistics. Several tools have been "*VELDified*" demonstrating general applicability and usefulness of VELD as a feasible approach for implementing the Transformation Toolbox.

⁹ Schöch, C., Dudar, J., & Fileva, E. (2023). Survey of Methods in Computational Literary Studies (= CLS INFRA D3.2: Series of Five Short Survey Papers on Methodological Issues) (v1.1.0). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892112> URL: <https://methods.clsinfra.io>

¹⁰ Ďurčo, M., Charvát, V. M., Resch, S., Börner, I., & Plank, L. (2023). CLS INFRA D6.3 Standards beyond TEI / Extended Transformation Matrix / Alternative Formats. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10209607>

¹¹ A relevant service in this context is the [SSH Open Marketplace](#), a central catalogue for tools and methods in the SSH community, featuring a comprehensive collection of Workflows – detailing the steps of various research tasks including the relevant resources used.

¹² on the topic of reproducibility of research, please read the underlying work by Christof Schöch:

1) Christof Schöch: "Replication or Reproduction or What? Modes of Repetitive Research in Computational Literary Studies". ExploreCor: Using Programmable Corpora in Computational Literary Studies (CLS INFRA Training School), Session Reproducibility in CLS Research. Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH OEAW), Vienna, June 10-12, 2024. [#200]

2) Christof Schöch: "Repetitive Research: A Conceptual Space and Terminology of Replication, Reproduction, Re-Implementation, Re-Analysis, and Re-Use in Digital Humanities", International Journal of Digital Humanities, 2023. – DOI: [10.1007/s42803-023-00073-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s42803-023-00073-y)

Finally, the [CLSCor catalogue](#) with its integrated [tool inventory](#) represents the registry of resources, the third component of the Transformation Toolbox. It uses the CLSCor ontology as a common data model to express the information about data and tools in a homogeneous manner and thus to enable interoperability matching, i.e. which tool can be used with which corpus (see section "[6.4 Tool Inventory as part of the CLSCor catalogue](#)").

Altogether task 6.2 proposes a novel technical concept to harmonise description of and improve interoperability between heterogeneous resources and delivered a proof-of-concept implementation validated on a comprehensive collection of real-world resources both corpora and tools.

4. Typical transformation paths and processing tasks

As mentioned in the introduction, the initial scope of the task 6.2 and of this deliverable was extended from pure format conversions of data, to encompass all kinds of data processing tasks, in which the resulting data may be enriched, i.e. contain additional information, or even be of very different nature altogether having little resemblance with the input data.

This chapter characterises the main kinds of processing paths employed in the context of CLS research and refers to the typical tools used for the individual tasks. For each step in the paths usually multiple different tools exist (e.g. various tokenisers or tools for NER), which differ in implementation, parameters and supported formats, often resulting in differing results for the same task on the same underlying data. Concrete examples for some of these paths are described in chapter "[7. Use cases](#)".

Two general approaches can be discerned to implement the paths, even though in practice, the implementations will combine these two approaches in differing measures:

- *distributed / loosely coupled* – components exist as independent stand-alone services and are called by a script or some kind of workflow management system passing the data from one to the next. Two examples for this approach are the [WebLicht](#) framework and the [Language Resources Switchboard](#), both developed in the context of the research infrastructure [CLARIN](#).
- *integrated environment* – all components of a path are integrated as part of one system, which controls the execution of the tasks hiding the inner workings, the wiring and flow of data between components from the user. Such a system usually also offers means for manual curation of data and enables seamless combination of automatic and manual tasks. Two prominent examples of such systems are [TEITOK](#) and [DraCor](#).
- *notebooks* – over the last years executable notebooks (e.g., [Jupyter Notebooks](#)) have become an immensely popular extraordinarily versatile means for all kinds of data processing tasks, especially well-suited for experimenting and for hybrid workflows combining non-interactive and interactive tasks.

By combining code and documentation and the easy sequential execution in the corresponding environment, they represent a hybrid between software, and training material, ideal for sharing, learning and reuse.

Notebooks do not fit cleanly into the distributed vs integrated distinction. They may use local tightly integrated modules, as well as remote services.

Independent of the actual processing task performed, all processing pipelines need to deal with the questions, how to retrieve the input data, where to "run" the processing task and where to store the resulting data, with the following general scenarios discernable:

- *all-local*: The basic "old-school" setup involves the user using their local computer running the code locally, with local data as input, storing the output on the same computer.
- *local data remote execution*: Increasingly, processing tasks are being performed by remote online services. If the data is stored locally, the user can upload it through some interface and then download the result.
- *remote data passed by reference*: If data is stored on a remote system and available online, it can be passed to the processing task "by reference", i.e. providing just a URL pointing to the data, leaving it up to the tool to resolve it and retrieve the data.

Data will be typically stored in a trusted repository and referenced by a Persistent Identifier (PID), but it can also be in a [GitHub](#) repository, or some cloud storage service.

The processing can be performed both remotely and locally. In the case of remote execution, the data does not pass through the user's local computer at all and is exchanged directly between remote systems, which is important especially with growing size of the data.

- *remote storing of results*: storing data to remote locations is more complicated than reading it, as it requires authentication and authorisation – only a known user can write to any system, while reading (getting the data) is often possible anonymously. However, there are mechanisms to enable a system to interact with another system on behalf of a user ([OAuth 2.0](#), [OIDC](#)). If these mechanisms are implemented, output data can be stored automatically e.g. to a GitHub repository, to [Zenodo](#), to [huggingface](#), or any other platform which exposes a REST API allowing to write data and supports the appropriate authentication mechanism.

4.1 Format conversion

Simply converting data to a different format was the original primary scope for the transformation paths and toolbox as foreseen in the project proposal. Typically, the goal is to preserve as much information contained in the original format as possible, using mappings between structural and semantic elements of the source and target format.

Outside of the CLS ecosystem, several general-purpose tools are available for the conversion of text-based data between common text-based formats, the most prominent one being [PanDoc](#) – "universal document converter" available as software to download and run locally. The TEI community maintains the [TEIGarage](#) service, also offering conversions from and to numerous formats, with stronger support for TEI-based documents. The SSH Open Marketplace, a catalogue of tools and methods in the SSH, [lists a number of conversion tools](#). Next to these dedicated tools, conversion between formats is implicitly supported by most tools offering more complex or specialised functionality by virtue of supporting multiple input and output formats. A few examples collected in D8.1 & D8.2 include but are not limited to SimpleCorp, TEITOK, DraCor or TXM desktop.

Even though in theory many formats for encoding textual data exist, the inventory of the data landscape compiled for the deliverable D6.3 revealed that in practice a handful of formats is by far the

most prevalent: TEI can be considered *lingua franca* in literary studies, while most NLP tools expect plain text as input and deliver output in some variant of the CONLL-U tabular format.

While converting TEI to plain text is trivial, usually the requirement is that the output of the processing (additional annotation layers) be merged with the original TEI encoding. This is usually achieved by initially stripping the source document of all existing encoding/elements and expressing it as stand-off annotation, passing only the plain text to the NLP processing. The enriched TEI is then reassembled combining the NLP output with the stand-off annotation. Multiple implementations for this task exist, two developed by teams at Charles University: [XML Annotation Tools](#) and [TEITOK Tools](#). While XML Annotation Tools are designed to support all XML formats and have certain expectations regarding the NLP tools used, TEITOK Tools are focused on TEI as input and output format and fine-tuned to work with UDPipe. Another system supporting this task is the [TXM](#) desktop and portal developed by Lyon¹³. These aforementioned tools are described in more detail in D8.2.

4.2 Automatic annotation and enrichment

The central epistemic object of CLS being a text corpus, a rich set of methods, both from computational literary studies and computational linguistics, can be applied to enrich and annotate the textual content, such as lemmatisation, part-of-speech tagging, NER, syntactic parsing, (semantic) entity linking, syllabification, rhyme detection.

These tasks have in common that they preserve the source text and add annotation layers grounded in the source text sequences. Usually, the basic unit into which the source text is divided and to which annotation layers refer to, are the tokens, output of a tokenisation task. While this task may seem trivial, there are in fact many nuances to it and with no community-wide convention, different systems may return differing results. Given that tokenisation is the initial task in any NLP processing pipeline, its implementation has a significant influence on all subsequent tasks.

A particularly challenging and increasingly important enrichment task is entity linking. While NER only categorises named entities occurring in text (as a person, place, institution, etc.) entity linking tries to identify the mentioned entities unambiguously by linking them to semantic entities defined in global reference resources like [Wikidata](#), [geonames](#), etc. Combining the text with rich semantic information contained in these knowledge graphs, e.g. events in the life of mentioned persons, relations between persons, or the geospatial information about geographical entities enables new means for analysis and exploration of the data.

The majority of the tools inventoried in D8.1 & D8.2 implement some of the automatic annotation methods. Either as part of an integrated user environment, including but not limited to TEITOK, or TXM portal, or as software library or a web service to be used programmatically (e.g. UDPipe, spaCy, NameTag, Averell, Horace, rhymetagger).

¹³ Heiden, S. (2010). The TXM Platform: Building Open-Source Textual Analysis Software Compatible with the TEI Encoding Scheme. In: 24th Pacific Asia Conference on Language, Information and Computation (pp. 389–398). Sendai, Japon. Retrieved from http://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/docs/00/54/97/64/PDF/pacli24_sheiden.pdf

4.3 Manual annotation

In the context of this deliverable, the focus is on automatic processing tools that perform their tasks without human intervention. However, it is important to emphasise that automatic processes and manual tasks usually need to be intertwined within hybrid workflows. In these scenarios, manually created data serves as the initial input for automatic processes, especially as training data in machine learning (ML)-based scenarios. Human input is continuously required to validate and further curate and refine the automatic results. Ideally, tools will integrate these two modes, allowing for quick iterations and seamless data flow between them. A prime example of such an integrated tool is TEITOK developed and provided by the team at Charles University. Other tools for manual annotation – based on D8.1 & D8.2 – are TXM desktop, conll-u editor, INCEpTION or Arborator Grew.

4.4 Analysis of text-based data

Even though the differentiation may not always be clear cut, one can distinguish between annotation tasks and analysis tasks, the latter generating new kinds of data that is not strictly bound to elements of the source text, such as information extraction or drama analysis.

Next to the very versatile research environments TEITOK and DraCor (specialised on analysis of drama corpora), tools like Kontext, Calc, Flair, QuitaUp offer different kinds of analyses.

4.5 Training Machine Learning models

AI-based approaches are rapidly becoming wide-spread applied for all kinds of processing tasks, from Automated Text Recognition (ATR) to all kinds of classifications, annotations, or extraction of structured semantic information, with corresponding Machine Learning models shared through several platforms or included in tools.

The applicability of individual models for a given dataset and task depends primarily on the underlying training data. Given that many available models are trained on data available online, representing largely current language, their performance deteriorates when applied to a particular kind of language usually dealt with in CLS, i.e. mainly historical and literary. On the other hand, training specialised models from scratch is prohibitively expensive. Therefore, more and more hybrid approaches are being applied, where existing base models are fine-tuned with small batches of bespoke training data, with very good results. Applications based on Large Language Models even achieve surprisingly high-quality results based on just a few examples or instructions (Zero-, One-, Few-shot learning).

The training process potentially involves many iterations with numerous batches of training data in combination with different possible model architectures and hyperparameter configurations. This poses a special challenge for data management and repeatability of the processes and reproducibility of the results involving ML-based methods. The VELD concept proposed in D6.2 suggests an answer to this challenge through a mechanism to encapsulate and persist all parts of a processing workflow (data, parameters, code).

4.6 Automated Text Recognition (ATR) – conversion of facsimile to text

When dealing with historical texts, one very important task is the conversion of scans of textual material to digital text. Even though this task has not been the focus of this project, it must be mentioned, as it is precondition to any further text-based processing and as such its quality has influence on all subsequent tasks.

Moreover, the approaches for ATR are getting increasingly complex, especially by integrating Large Language Models (LLMs) becoming more "language aware", not only dramatically improving the recognition rate, but delivering a feature-rich output.

A central requirement for the ATR is the availability of ground truth, i.e. manually transcribed data that can be used to train the models. Even though many factors influence the quality of the result – layout, typesetting or hand writing, language, time period, genre – and ideally a custom-tailored model is needed for every source, meanwhile this can be achieved easily by starting with an existing model and fine-tuning it with relatively small amounts human-encoded training data specific for given source.

Probably the most widely used ATR tool offered as a service is [Transkribus](#), which offers an integrated environment for transcribing text and training custom models. Many of the models are publicly available. [Kraken](#), [Tesseract](#) are another two widely used ATR tools, available as software. Furthermore, eScriptorium is both a [software](#) for transcribing text, as well as an integrated environment offered as a [service](#) that allows training of custom models using kraken as the ATR engine in the background.

5. Design and conceptual considerations

This chapter details the design considerations and decisions underlying the Transformation Toolbox.

As stated in the [introduction and methodology section above](#), conceptually, the Transformation Toolbox consists of three parts:

- a) Tooling – actual software or services to process and transform data
- b) Interoperability mechanism to harmonise the use of heterogeneous tools and data
- c) A registry of available tools and data capturing information about their technical characteristics

The various tools for processing and transforming tasks have been provided by individual project partners (cf. D8.1, D8.2, D8.3, D8.4, D8.5), or are available as free, open source tools. They are described through metadata and represented in the CLSCor Tool Inventory serving as the central registry. The conceptual basis for the registry is described in the section "[5.1 Transformation Matrix](#)", and its implementation is outlined in chapter "[6. Integration with the CLSCor data model and catalogue](#)".

The interoperability mechanism is the central contribution of task 6.2. It is described in more detail in section "[5.3 VELD - Versioned Executable Logic and Data](#)".

5.1 Transformation Matrix

As laid out in D6.1, the conceptual basis for the transformation toolbox is the so-called Transformation Matrix, which allows structured description of certain characteristics for both data and tools, necessary to identify which of them are compatible/interoperable and in which cases transformations are needed.

D6.1 argues that it is by far not sufficient to perform the matching based just on the file format, but rather also the underlying schema and the specific features manifested in the data have to be considered. This needs to be combined with the method one wishes to apply to the data (e.g. tokenisation or NER). In practice, format, schema, individual features, as well as methods are intricately intertwined. As an example: if one wishes to apply the *method* part of speech tagging with *tool A* on a set of documents from *corpus C*, the tool must support the *format* of the corpus documents. However, depending on the tool, the document may need to feature explicitly annotated tokens, a result of the method tokenisation. On the other hand, in *tool B*, the tokenisation may be already included as part of the internal NLP pipeline, however it may expect a different format or schema for the input data.

The descriptions for data and tools have to be structured, formalised, consistent, so that they can be used for findability/discoverability as well as facilitating interoperability. To achieve this consolidation a common data model, the CLSCor ontology, has been developed accompanied by controlled vocabularies to harmonise and canonise the terminology, allowing to capture information about both data and tools in a consistent manner.

So, while the Transformation Matrix was the initial abstract conceptualisation at the beginning of the project, the CLSCor ontology is its formal representation and the CLSCor catalogue with the Tool Inventory its instantiation. These are described in more detail in chapter "[6. Integration with CLSCor the data model and catalogue](#)".

5.2 Processing as part of the research workflow

Even though this deliverable concentrates on the data processing tasks, it is important to consider them as part of the overall research workflow (or "research data lifecycle") as well. This has a plethora of variant manifestations, however following main steps can be discerned:

1. discover (data)
2. retrieve data
3. process - iterations of manual and automatic annotation
4. index & search
5. analyse & visualise
6. store and publish

The following diagram makes an attempt to map various technical components of an ecosystem onto these generic steps of the research life cycle, representing the reference architecture for the Transformation Toolbox.

5.3 VELD - Versioned Executable Logic and Data

This chapter introduces the VELD (Versioned Executable Logic and Data) concept together with some reflections on the initial design decisions. A full technical specification is published here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13322913>.

VELD is a generic mechanism to

- harmonise and streamline the use of heterogeneous tools
- improve interoperability between heterogeneous resources
- combine resources into multi-step/complex processing pipelines
- ensure reproducibility and repeatability of complex processing pipelines

thus, answering to the central requirements of the Transformation Toolbox. VELD is primarily a design pattern accompanied by a reference implementation and metadata schema. The design pattern defines the conceptual framework which may be implemented with any suitable tools, albeit Git and

Docker is used for the reference implementation. The metadata schema serves as a consistent blueprint to describe all VELD objects.

Even though originally conceived as solution to harmonisation and interoperability challenge addressed in task 6.2, the VELD approach is applicable not only for format conversions, but for any processing tasks, including NLP annotations (tokenisation, lemmatisation, PoS, NER) and various kinds of analysis (network, collocation, drama, etc.). Within the CLS INFRA project, numerous tools were "VELDified", i.e. wrapped/represented as VELD objects and used/included in reproducible workflows.

All these VELD objects are currently collected under an umbrella GitHub organisation ([VELDhub](#)). These tools and workflows cover a varied selection of modern CLS and NLP use cases and demonstrate the general applicability of the VELD concept. A demonstrative selection of such workflows is further discussed within this deliverable in chapter "[7. Use cases](#)".

VELD as design pattern

As a design pattern, only three distinct types of VELD objects are defined (colloquially called "velds"): **data**, **code**, and **chain** velds. Data and code velds are expressed in their own atomic Git repositories, forming independent units. Within those units, data velds only contain static serialised data and code velds contain source code and build instructions. Chain velds then combine the atomic data and code velds into processing pipelines, primarily by using Git submodules. This means that the entire context is made explicit and persistent, containing the data veld that was used as input for a code veld and the resulting data veld output. This distinction into three types of objects allows for vastly increased flexibility as data and code repositories can be freely recombined across different, but still suitable contexts. At the same time, it ensures stability, since the state of a chain repository is manifested as a commit and also references the states of its contained Git submodules via their respective commits. Through this, the entire state of a composite workflow and its components reliably persisted even though the components are independent entities on their own. Usually, flexibility and stability are mutually exclusive system characteristics, but through the VELD design pattern, both can be achieved simultaneously. In addition to this compositional mechanism, the reproducible execution is achieved by utilising the docker, more specifically Docker Compose files. Docker is a widely used virtualisation technology, allowing to abstract away runtime environments from the host OS environment. VELD thus offers the same benefits that Docker Compose does: a declarative highly reproducible encapsulation of arbitrary code stacks. Also, both code and chain velds are primarily defined through their Docker Compose files, marking their persistable and versionable execution points. Each code veld can be executed on its own independent of versioned data context. This enables ad-hoc usage, convenient downstream usage and quick experimentations, while chain velds enable precise reproduction of the entire context by persisting it as commits in its own repository and in its submodule repositories.

To summarise, the design principles of VELD are:

- Encapsulation of code and data into atomic reusable components
- Flexible aggregation of atomic repositories into cohesive units
- Increased reproducibility of code and its entire project and data context
- Utilisation of a minimal set of proven stable technologies

- Avoiding creating additional software
- Flexibility through a distributed design

VELD as metadata schema

A defining aspect of the veld objects is their consistent self-description following a formal metadata schema. This schema enables discoverability, informs about the "signature" of the encapsulated code, i.e. the input and output parameters which facilitates interoperability and the composition of data and code velds into chain velds. The metadata schema is formally defined in a dedicated Git repository which includes a validator ([VELD specification](#)). Any yaml file that adheres to this schema, becomes a valid veld object and offers its standalone usage or potential composition into chain velds. Additionally, such a veld yaml file is a valid Docker Compose file in the case of code and chain velds. This makes the veld yaml file the central authority on both its description and technical execution, both done in a declarative and persistable manner. Besides describing its technical parameters for interoperability, a verbose metadata section also serves as a source for discovery mechanism - a central registry, necessitated by the distributed nature of the VELD design. A minimal prototype of such a registry is currently implemented in a dedicated Git repository ([VELD registry](#)). Next to this registry, information about velds is also integrated in the CLSCor catalogue, one of the main channels for dissemination of products created by the CLS INFRA project. For this, an automatic transformation was implemented that converts VELD metadata to the CLSCor model. This allows the implemented veld objects to be registered and aggregated in the central catalogue of the CLS INFRA project, while the VELD metadata schema can be defined in its own scope independent of the CLSCor model, avoiding a dependency of VELD on CLS resources and outcomes.

Architectural design discussion

Designing an overarching consistent framework aggregating heterogeneous data processing workflows, as was required by the project's goals, is a complex undertaking that requires critical evaluations of potential architectural implementations.

Several existing technologies and architectural designs were tested and prototyped, among which were [prefect](#), [airflow](#), [MLflow](#), [kubernetes](#), [Weblicht](#) and many more. This initial evaluation made a principal conflict apparent, which was already touched upon above: between an integrated/centralised and a modular/distributed architecture. While neither architectural design can be deemed as ultimately superior over the other, both have their distinct benefits and drawbacks depending on context. To quickly recap and simplify: An integrated/centralised architecture is where several distinct functionalities are aggregated within a single monolithic runtime. This does generally offer higher consistency of all functionalities and user experience and also increases stability; but at the expense of flexibility. While a modular/distributed architecture achieves the inverse. In an integrated architecture, consistency often comes at a higher implementation cost, since it requires high quality software development throughout the entire codebase, and even more so the wider and heterogeneous the domain is. Given the heterogeneity of the CLS and NLP ecosystems coupled with rapid advancements in technology, it renders it difficult to develop an integrated architecture that aims to unite the manifold resources of these domains under one consistent framework. Especially so, considering the development resources available in the CLS INFRA project. Furthermore, even if such an architecture could be achieved, it would require constant maintenance not only to keep it

running as it is, but also to keep it up to date with the ongoing fast-paced development within the NLP / CLS tooling landscape. As an example, the *Weblicht* platform is a polished consistent platform integrating a number of NLP tools, allowing to define and execute a range of workflows, but it imposes the adoption of TCF – the Text Corpus Format as the one common exchange format by tools to be incorporated, restricting the applicability to a rather narrow set of NLP tasks. On top of these challenges, an integrated architecture has the critical drawback of relying on a single or just a few runtimes (e.g. a python interpreter), which severely limits incorporations of more third party libraries as they bring in their own dependencies, leading to widely experienced "dependency hell" problems, where conflicting dependencies create mutually inconsistent states.

In contrast to an integrated approach, the modular distributed design exhibits inverse characteristics. In a modular distributed architecture, the functionalities are spread across distinct environments, with single responsibilities assigned to each. These environments are usually implemented in containers, foremost docker, with some overarching orchestration platform. This design is also commonly referred to as microservice architecture. It is inherently more flexible but requires careful design considerations and coordination between different stakeholders to reduce sprawling inconsistency between modules. Furthermore, since the modules of such a system are independent units, aggregating them into a consistent platform acting as a focal point as envisioned by CLS INFRA, becomes more difficult the more functionalities such a platform should offer. Especially difficult is not only theoretical harmonisation of a module interface but their real-time interactions when executed. Passing data reliably between modules in a distributed system is an inherently difficult task requiring substantial orchestration efforts. There are numerous technical approaches to these problems, notably due the microservice architecture having grown in popularity over the past decade. But even these can easily deteriorate or impose high implementation and maintenance costs due to the inherent conflict between modular distributed components and an overarching consistent management platform.

Based on all these considerations, it was decided to adopt a modular distributed architecture for implementing the Transformation Toolbox. As a consequence, the system lacks a central platform offering web-based execution of processing workflows. However, while the execution is left to the user, the system offers a registry for discovering tools and workflows, and a harmonised way to use them. Moreover, it offers high flexibility with regards to the range of offered tools and adaptable contexts, as well as improved reproducibility, and better sustainability by isolating inner complexities of individual components in self-contained distributable environments (Docker containers).

6. Integration with the CLSCor data model and catalogue

As described in chapter "[5. Design and conceptual considerations](#)", one component of the Transformation Toolbox is a registry of tools and data including a harmonised, formalised structured description of their characteristics. The [CLSCor ontology](#) together with a set of [controlled vocabularies](#), originally focused on describing data (Corpora) were extended to serve as a common data model to express information about both data and tools. Information about tools from two sources has been converted to adhere to this model and ingested to form the [Tool Inventory](#) module of the [CLSCor catalogue](#). This chapter devotes individual sections to a) changes to CLSCor ontology, b) the workflows to populate the Tool Inventory, c) changes to CLSCor catalogue to incorporate the Tool Inventory.

6.1 Updates to the CLSCor ontology

To allow harmonised description of both data and tools, the CLSCor ontology, initially developed to describe literary corpora, their structure and characteristics (as proposed in D6.1), was extended to allow expressing also information about tools.

class (crmcls ¹⁴)	subClassOf/equivalentClass	tool specific properties (crmcls)
X3_Feature	crm:E73_Information_Object crm:E58_Measurement_Unit	Y9i_input_is_expected_by Y10i_output_is_generated_by
X5_Research_Activity	crm:E7_Activity	Y7_uses
X6_Method	crm:E29_Design_or_Procedure	Y8i_is_implemented_by Y9_expects_input Y10_generates_output
X7_Format	pem:PE43_Encoding_Type (owl:equivalentClass)	Y9i_input_is_expected_by Y10i_output_is_generated_by
X8_Schema	pem:PE38_Schema (owl:equivalentClass)	Y9i_input_is_expected_by Y10i_output_is_generated_by
X12_Tool	crm:E1_CRM_Entity	Y7_uses Y7i_is_used_by Y8_implements Y9_expects_input Y10_generates_output
X13_Tool_Description	crm:E83_Type_Creation	

Table 1: CLSCor classes, CIDOC CRM sub classes or owl equivalent classes, and tool specific properties

Table 1 above lists the already existing classes for Feature, Method, Format and Schema, which have now been enhanced with new tool specific properties. Additionally, the class X5 Research Activity and two new classes for the Tool (X12) itself and its Tool Description Event (X13) are introduced. Table 2 below details the newly added properties, their domain and range and provides a short description of their purpose.

¹⁴ The namespace "crmcls" applies for the whole column. All namespaces are listed in the Appendix, section [10.1 List of prefixes and namespaces](#)

property (crmcls)	domain (crmcls)	range (crmcls)	description
Y7_uses	X5_Research_Activity X12_Tool	X12_Tool	to express that a tool is compatible/can be used by/integrated with another tool and to express that a tool is used for a research activity
Y8_implements	X12_Tool	X6_Method	to express that a tool implements a method
Y9_expects_input	X6_Method X12_Tool	X3_Feature X7_Format X8_Schema	to express that a tool expects a certain feature, format or schema as input
Y10_generates_output	X6_Method X12_Tool	X3_Feature X7_Format X8_Schema	to express that a tool generates a certain feature, format or schema as output

Table 2: CLSCor properties, their domain and range, and a short description

6.2 Populating the CLSCor Tool Inventory

The CLSCor tool inventory contains information about tools from the following main sources: The overview compiled in D8.1 (updated and enhanced in D8.2) as well as tools and scripts developed within D8.3, D8.4 and D8.5¹⁵ and the registry of VELDs. Even though these sources provided certain structured information about the tools, a massive curation and data processing effort was needed to harmonise and normalise this information and express it adhering to the CLSCor ontology.

Though the VELD framework features a central registry of existing velds, it is considered independent from and in principle "unaware" of the CLS scope. This implies that information from the VELD registry is pulled and processed on the side of CLS infrastructure.

Altogether, the CLSCor tool inventory currently features 31 items included from D8.1 & D8.2 and 139 from the VELD registry.

The initial phase in the conversion process of the semi-structured and verbose information provided within the D8.1 and D8.2 deliverables involved the transformation of the PDF data into an Excel sheet. While certain descriptive texts could be adopted easily as general information for each tool, other entries had to be carefully filtered, consolidated, restructured and mapped to the existing CLSCor vocabularies, sometimes prompting the need to add new terms. Whereas the input and output formats yielded only a limited number of new vocabulary terms, the major and most time-intensive task of breaking down and consolidating the information about methods and features mixed in one field into individual values resulted in numerous new terms and descriptions for both the feature and method vocabularies. Additionally, a small new vocabulary was introduced for operating systems, since the information provided was already easy to reuse and to adapt as a vocabulary. In instances where a consolidated or shortened vocabulary term was inadequate to fully express the original information provided, the original description was appended as a comment (e.g., the original

¹⁵ Deliverables 8.3, 8.4, and 8.5 are not yet published, but will focus on tools and notebooks for NER, relation extraction and sentiment analysis. See also: <https://github.com/GhentCDH/CLSinfra>

description for the operating system of the tool "conll-u editor" states "the server runs on Linux, but the annotation runs in web browsers across operating systems", while the vocabulary term only uses "Linux"). Subsequent consolidation steps entailed typing the links provided for each tool using the link-type vocabulary and breaking the list of related papers into individual table rows.

In order to feed the data from the table into the catalogue, it first had to be mapped to the CLSCor data model, enhancing the data model in the process, and then transformed to TTL.

The newly introduced classes X12_Tool and X13_Tool_Description were used to capture the task of describing tools as meta-information and metadata on tools collected in the WP8 deliverables. The X13_Tool_Description mechanism allows to assert where the information comes from and who were its contributors.

E41_Appellation was used to model the tool name and its variants:

```
https://clscor.io/entity/[tool1] a crmcls:X12_Tool;
  crm:P1_is_identified_by https://clscor.io/entity/[appellation1].

https://clscor.io/entity/[appellation1] a crm:E41_Appellation;
  crm:P2_has_type https://clscor.io/entity/type/appellation/tool_name;
  rdf:value "IMS Corpus Workbench".
```

Links connected to each tool were typed, using the [link-type vocabulary](#) to differentiate the links from each other (e.g., api, tutorial, documentation, info website, docker instance, exploration ui, data repository, etc.):

```
https://clscor.io/entity/[tool2] a crmcls:X12_Tool;
  crm:P1_is_identified_by https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-notebooks.

https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-notebooks a crm:E42_Identifier;
  crm:P2_has_type https://clscor.io/entity/type/link/tutorial;
  rdf:value "Link to the DraCor Notebooks tutorial".
```

Information on methods, features, languages, licenses, operating systems, and input/output formats, which could be mapped to the CLSCor vocabularies, was added to X13 with an E13_Attribute_Assignment mechanism, similar to the X9_Corpus_Description used for the initial collection of literary corpora in the CLSCor catalogue:

```
https://clscor.io/entity/[attrAssign1] a crm:E13_Attribute_Assignment;
  crm:P134_continued https://clscor.io/entity/[toolDescEvent1];
  crm:P140_assigned_attribute_to https://clscor.io/entity/[tool3];
  crm:P141_assigned
    https://clscor.io/entity/type/method/coreference_chain_search;
  crm:P177_assigned_property_of_type crmcls:Y8_implements;
  crm:P3_has_note "Search in an annotated text corpus (co-reference)".
```

All other metadata consisting of more verbose descriptions which could not be mapped to existing CLSCor vocabularies and/or further consolidated, was connected to X12_Tool via a specific typed note mechanism, used in the [SARI project](#). As normal P3_has_note modelling combines all formulated

descriptions into one single literal, typed notes allow more granular information to be individually attached to the tool with a P3.1_has_type, containing (in case of the tool inventory) the name of the table column:

```
https://clscor.io/entity/[tool4] a crmcls:X12_Tool;
  crm:P01i_is_domain_of https://clscor.io/entity/note/1,
  https://clscor.io/entity/note/2.
```

```
https://clscor.io/entity/note/1 a crm:PC3_has_note;
  crm:P3.1_has_type https://clscor.io/entity/[tool_description];
  crm:P03_has_range_literal "This tool allows you to manually create or
  edit corpora annotated with Universal Dependencies. It provides a
  particularly user-friendly tokenization editing; that is, it is very
  easy to delete, split or merge tokens or sentences - a feature that is
  not automatically provided with annotation tools! Also, the sentences
  can be visualized as trees or flat graphs or tables."
```

```
https://clscor.io/entity/note/2 a crm:PC3_has_note;
  crm:P3.1_has_type https://clscor.io/entity/[text_processing];
  crm:P03_has_range_literal "It loads a CoNLL-U file and allows you to
  edit it."
```

This approach made it possible to keep the more verbose yet consolidated and differentiated descriptions from the WP8 deliverables on the general tool introduction, versions, distribution, user interface, text processing, statistical models, metric, visualisation, formalism, tagset, and related papers while supporting the front end in providing and displaying this data in an organised manner.

Once there was an initial version of the mapping and modelling, [CLSCorGI](#) – a bespoke python transformation script developed at the [ACDH-CH](#) for creating CLSCor compliant RDF from tabular data – was used to transform the tool metadata (gathered in D8.1+D8.2) into a TTL serialisation. After multiple iterations of refinements to the mapping and code based on manual checking of the output, the transformed metadata was ingested into the CLSCor catalogue. The extension of the catalogue frontend allowing to display this tool information is described in section "[6.4 Tool Inventory as part of the CLSCor catalogue](#)".

6.3 Converting VELD objects to the CLSCor model

VELD and the CLSCor catalogue serve distinct purposes, VELD deals with tool encapsulation and CLSCor catalogue is for description and discovery of tools and corpora, however both deal with the same entities - the tools. And while VELD is meant to be conceptually independent of CLSCor, given that CLSCor catalogue aspires to provide a comprehensive overview of relevant tools, it should contain all the tools from the VELD domain. To this end, a mechanism was introduced to convert VELD metadata to the CLSCor data model for automatic ingestion into the catalogue. This conversion was implemented through an ad hoc python script based on a conceptual mapping from metadata fields used for describing the veld objects to classes and properties defined by the CLSCor ontology. Several automatic schema tools were evaluated (jsonschema, jsonpath, jamespath) that could in theory perform a declarative, automatic pattern-matching between the source (VELD yaml files) and target

data (CLSCor ontology). The bulk of data could be converted in such a way, however several edge cases had proven too costly, and so ultimately custom python functions were implemented for each mapping, with a small DSL (domain specific language) embedded directly into the codebase: https://github.com/acdh-oew/VELD_registry/blob/main/data/clscor_conversion/mapping.py.

6.4 Tool Inventory as part of the CLSCor catalogue

The [CLSCor catalogue](#) in its initial version featured views to explore information about corpora, corpus documents and authors. Within task 6.2, it has been extended to present also information about tools, serving as Tool Inventory, a comprehensive registry of tools.

It consists of a searchable list of all the tools leading to a detail page for each tool containing information about the input and output formats, methods it implements and all the other special properties as described in the section on extensions to the CLSCor data model.

Following screenshot shows the Tool inventory listing all the tools.

Tools

This page provides an inventory of tools for processing texts compiled during the CLS INFRA project. The data consists of curated and harmonised information from the deliverables [D8.1](#) (updated and enhanced in [D8.2](#)) as well as tools and scripts developed within the project and the [registry of VELDs](#) (for more information on VELD check out the [VELD technical concept](#) and [D6.2](#) (link will follow)).

The list below shows the tool's name, the methods it implements and features it produces (if applicable).

View and search all 170 tools

🔍 Filter Results

TOOL	METHODS	FEATURES
train_infer_wordembeddings_multiple_architectures_amc_preprocess_sample(chain_veld)	applying NLP methods, information extraction	
automatic_tei-ification_of_gutenberg_step1_download_gutenberg_metadata(chain_veld)	information extraction	
teitok-tools_parseudpipe(code_veld)	information extraction, tokenization, applying NLP methods, applying universal dependencies	
apis_ner_transform_to_gold(chain_veld)	information extraction	
downloader(code_veld)	information extraction	
TEITOK	annotating, annotation editing, applying NLP methods, applying textometry methods, corpus management, information extraction, statistical analysis, collocations analysis, event extraction, linear text search, manual annotation, network analysis, sentence splitting, syntactic tree search, tokenization	syntactic tree matching a query, text snippet matching a query, sentence borders, network graph with characters as nodes and interactions as edges, network graph, token

Following screenshot shows a detail view describing one tool, taking DraCor as an example.

DraCor

URI:
<https://clscor.io/entity/7a7b90c69f>

Description:
 DraCor simplifies accessing specific parts of a TEI annotated dramatic texts (such as the spoken text per character, spoken text of characters by gender, stage directions, etc.) DraCor automatically extracts textual features (e. g. number of characters, speeches, scenes, etc.), generates networks based on co-occurrences of characters in a scene, and calculates network metrics. The derived data can be exported in various formats, e.g., JSON, CSV, RDF but also specialized formats, e.g., GEXF format to be used in Gephi, a tool for network analysis. The DraCor API offers numerous options and additional formats for further processing of the unified metadata. A local instance of the DraCor system can be set up using Docker, which can be used to work with custom corpora or in copyright material.

Link:
<https://dracor.org/> (info website, project website)
<https://dracor.org/doc/api> (api)
<https://github.com/dracor-org> (data repository)
<https://fortext.net/ressourcen/textsammlungen/dracor-drama-corpora-project> (info website)
<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-notebooks> (tutorial)
<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-api> (api)
<https://hub.docker.com/u/dracor> (docker instance)

Methods:
[Applying Textometry Methods](#)
[Corpus Management](#)
[Drama Analysis](#)
[Information Extraction](#)
[Network Analysis](#)
[Statistical Analysis](#)

Features:
[Act](#)
[Name Of Character](#)
[Network Graph With Characters As Nodes And Interactions As Edges](#)
[Number Of Characters](#)
[Number Of Plays](#)
[Number Of Tokens](#)
[Scene](#)
[Segment](#)

[Spoken Text By Character](#)
[Spoken Text By Gender](#)
[Stage Directions](#)

Input format:
 TEI

Output format:
 CSV
 JSON
 TEI
 GEXF
 XML RDF

Distribution:
 Cloud service

Text_processing:
 Returns some metrics as numbers or tables.
 Returns some visualization (plots, interactive elements, etc.).

User_interface:
 GUI, API-REST

Version:
 v0.87.1

Version_date:
 2022-12-30

Related Papers:

- Börner, I., & Trilcke, P. (2023). CLS INFRA D7.1 On Programmable Corpora. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7664964>
- Fischer, F., Börner, I., Göbel, M., Hechtl, A., Kittel, C., Milling, C., & Trilcke, P. (2019, Juli 10). Programmable Corpora: Introducing DraCor, an Infrastructure for the Research on European Drama. DH2019: »Complexities«. 9–12 July 2019. Book of Abstracts. DH2019 »Complexities«, Utrecht. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4284002>
- Trilcke, P., Ustinova, E., Börner, I., Fischer, F., & Milling, C. (2022, September 14). Detecting Small Worlds in a Corpus of Thousands of Theatre Plays. A DraCor Study in Comparative Literary Network Analysis [Conference Version]. Workshop on Computational Drama Analysis: Achievements and Opportunities, Cologne. https://github.com/dracor-org/small-world-paper/raw/conference-version/Detecting_Small_World_Networks_in_a_Huge_Multilingual_Corpus_of_Theater_Plays.pdf

7. Use cases

This chapter describes a few concrete examples of complex processing workflows implemented using VELD. More tools and workflows can be found in the [VELD registry](#) as well as in the [CLSCor Tool Inventory](#).

7.1 TEI-fication of a corpus on the Gutenberg example

Goal: Automatically transform texts from plain txt to TEI.

Description: The [Gutenberg corpus](#) contains many books not expressed as TEI XML but only as plain text files. This processing chain repository downloads German books and automatically transforms them to TEI XML with the help of TEITOK-tools. Additionally, since project Gutenberg does not offer a native API which could be programmatically queried to find the relevant books, a custom triplestore¹⁶ is set up and ingested with Gutenberg metadata so that the entire catalogue can be queried in a reproducible structured manner.

¹⁶ a triplestore is a "purpose-built database for the storage and retrieval of triples" (source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Triplestore>)

Data and tools used:

- [Gutenberg corpus](#)
- [TEITOK-tools](#)
- [udpipe](#)
- [Apache Jena Fuseki](#)
- [TEITOK-tools](#)

Repo: https://github.com/veldhub/veld_chain_automatic_tei-ification_of_gutenberg

step	input	method	output
1: download gutenberg RDF Metadata and extract	URL	information extraction	RDF xml file
2: set up a triplestore (blazegraph)	Blazegraph software package	using a triplestore	running instance of a triple store
3: load RDF data into fuseki triplestore	RDF xml file	information extraction	RDF data in a triplestore
4: query RDF data for German books that have TXT files but no TEI XML files, export download urls into csv	RDF data in a triplestore	information extraction	list of URLs to text files as CSV
5: download all plain text files	List of URLs to text files as CSV	information extraction	set of plain text files
6: bulk convert txt files to TEI XML with teitok tools	set of plain text files	applying NLP methods	set of TEI/XML files

Table 3: Individual workflow steps for the TEI-fication of a corpus on the Gutenberg example

7.2 Run ELTeC through UDPipe

Goal: Apply NLP tools on a TEI-encoded Corpus

Description: This processing chain repository downloads several ELTeC corpora (Czech, English, French, German, Spanish), converts TEI/XML files to plain text files, executes udipec inferences on them and analyses the enriched data delivering statistics about various linguistic annotations such as distinct lemma counts or distribution of part-of-speech tags.

Data and tools used:

- [ELTeC](#)
- [Conllu editor](#)
- [Jupyter notebook](#)
- [UDPipe](#)
- [XSLT](#)

Repo: https://github.com/veldhub/veld_chain_eltec_udpipe_inference

step	input	method	output
1: convert TEI/XML data to plain text files	set of TEI files	information extraction	set of plain text files (TXT)
2: download udpipe models	URL	information extraction	UDPipe models
3: use UDPipe inferencing on raw texts	set of plain text files (TXT), UDPipe models	applying NLP methods	set of files with annotations in CONLL-U format
4: analyse enriched files for their linguistic characteristics	set of files with annotations in CONLL-U format	applying NLP methods	statistics about distributions of features
5: inspect individual conllu files with ConllEditor	set of files with annotations in CONLL-U format	applying NLP methods	data visualisations

Table 4: Individual workflow steps for running ELTeC through UDPipe

7.3 Alternative tokenisations

Goal: Apply two different tokenisation tools on the same data and compare results

Description: Downloads test data, runs two different tokenisation tools on it, and compares statistically their differences in output

Data and tools used:

- [Gutenberg corpus](#)
- [Jupyter notebook](#)
- [TEITOK-tools](#)
- [XML annotation tools](#)

Repo: https://github.com/veldhub/veld_chain_compare_tokenizations

step	input	method	output
1: download a book from Project Gutenberg	URL	information extraction	TXT file
2: run xmlanntools	TXT file	tokenisation	TEI XML
3: run teitok-tools	TXT file	tokenisation	TEI XML
4: compare outputs	two TEI/XML files	applying NLP methods	a diff showing differences between the two files

Table 5: Individual workflow steps for alternative tokenisations

7.4 Semantic drift analysis of DTA

Goal: Train several static word embeddings models to analyse semantic drift

Description: These processing chains use a corpus of German texts from "Deutsches Textarchiv" (DTA) with publication dates ranging from the 15th century to modernity. The texts are downloaded, pre-

processed and then used as input for training several static word embeddings models. These models are then used to identify semantic drifts of example words by comparing the differences in vector representations for different time periods.

Data and tools used:

- [DTA corpus](#)
- [Jupyter notebook](#)
- [Word2vec](#)
- [XSLT](#)

Repo: https://github.com/veldhub/veld_chain_dta_semantic_drift_analysis

step	input	method	output
1: download DTA data	URL	information extraction	set of TEI/XML files
2: convert TEI to plain text	set of TEI/XML files	information extraction	set of plain text files
3: train several word2vec models	set of plain text files	applying NLP methods	word2vec model
4: compare word embeddings of trained model (using Jupyter notebooks)	word2vec model	applying NLP methods	statistics, data visualisations

Table 6: Individual workflow steps for a semantic drift analysis of DTA

8. Conclusion and outlook

This deliverable described the work in task 6.2 aiming to facilitate the comparability and integration among corpora as well as the use of these corpora with various processing tools. To overcome the heterogeneity and incoherence of the CLS ecosystem and to improve the interoperability between data and tools, the originally intended scope of the task – providing means for converting data between formats – has been extended, proposing a more general mechanism to harmonise the use of heterogeneous distributed resources in any kind of processing tasks.

Main contributions of task 6.2:

- VELD as a novel technical concept – a generic mechanism to harmonise description of and improve interoperability between heterogeneous resources and to construct processing pipelines combining heterogeneous tools using widely adopted well-established technologies, which at the same time ensures reproducibility of the workflows.
- a proof-of-concept implementation of the Transformation Toolbox
- a comprehensive collection of real-world resources both corpora and tools
- Tool Inventory implemented as part of the CLSCor catalogue - a registry offering a comprehensive structured overview of tools developed or made available within CLS INFRA project including information on their capabilities and applicability
- Extension to CLSCor ontology to allow description of tools
- A number of tools - "VELDified" – made available according to the VELD concept.

These outcomes represent solid ground stones, however further substantive efforts are required to deliver a stable technical infrastructure that will become an integral part of everyday scholarly processes. Major areas of further development are:

- Controlled vocabularies (especially for describing features, formats and methods) were formed based on disparate, often unformalised resource descriptions.
These need to be further consolidated and validated by scholars
- Continuous curation of metadata describing tools and corpus data
- Expanding the coverage of the resources in the CLSCor catalogue, especially through automatic ingestion of metadata about documents of a corpus
- Matching functionality able to propose valid combinations of data and tools based their technical characteristics

Nevertheless, contributing to the overall objectives of the project, this task delivered concepts and designs for constructing a technical infrastructure for CLS domain supported through various prototypes and proof-of-concept reference implementation. It also made a significant contribution to the consolidation of the CLS ecosystem by proposing a unifying data model and using it to describe sizeable collections of data and tools, offering a comprehensive overview of resources available in the domain.

9. References

9.1 Publications

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- Heiden, S. (2010). The TXM Platform: Building Open-Source Textual Analysis Software Compatible with the TEI Encoding Scheme. In: 24th Pacific Asia Conference on Language, Information and Computation (pp. 389–398). Sendai, Japon. Retrieved from http://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/docs/00/54/97/64/PDF/pacific24_sheiden.pdf
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Schöch, C. (2024). Replication or Reproduction or What? Modes of Repetitive Research in Computational Literary Studies. ExploreCor: Using Programmable Corpora in Computational Literary Studies (CLS INFRA Training School), Session Reproducibility in CLS Research. Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH OEAW), Vienna, June 10-12, 2024. [#200]

Schöch, C. (2023). Repetitive Research: A Conceptual Space and Terminology of Replication, Reproduction, Re-Implementation, Re-Analysis, and Re-Use in Digital Humanities. International Journal of Digital Humanities, 2023. – DOI: 10.1007/s42803-023-00073-y.

9.2 Collection of links and websites mentioned in D6.2

All websites are listed in order of their appearance in the text and were last accessed in February 2025.

- JCLS: <https://jcls.io/>
- CCLS: <https://jcls.io/site/conference/>
- Weblight: <https://weblight.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/weblight/>
- Language Resources Switchboard: <https://switchboard.clarin.eu/tools>
- CLARIN: <https://www.clarin.eu/>
- TEITOK: <http://www.teitok.org/>
- DraCor: <https://dracor.org/>
- Jupyter Notebooks: <https://jupyter.org/>
- GitHub: <https://github.com/>
- OAuth 2.0: <https://oauth.net/2/>
- OIDC: <https://openid.net/>
- Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/>
- huggingface: <https://huggingface.co/>
- PanDoc: <https://pandoc.org/>
- TEIGarage: <https://teigarage.tei-c.org/>
- SSH Open Marketplace (list of conversion tools):
<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/search?order=score&f.source=Conversion+Hub>
- XML Annotation Tools: <https://github.com/czcorpus/xmlanntools>
- TEITOK Tools: <https://github.com/ufal/teitok-tools/>
- Wikidata: <https://www.wikidata.org>
- geonames: <https://www.geonames.org/>
- Transkribus: <https://www.transkribus.org/>
- Kraken: <https://kraken.re/main/index.html>
- Tesseract: <https://tesseract-ocr.github.io/>
- Git: <https://git-scm.com/>
- Docker: <https://www.docker.com/>
- VELDhub: <https://github.com/veldhub>
- VELD specification: https://github.com/acdh-oeaw/VELD_spec
- VELD registry: https://github.com/acdh-oeaw/VELD_registry
- Prefect: <https://www.prefect.io/>

- Airflow: <https://airflow.apache.org/>
- MLflow: <https://mlflow.org/>
- Kubernetes: <https://kubernetes.io/>
- CLSCor ontology: <https://gitlab.clsinfra.io/cls-infra/wp567/clscor/-/blob/main/model/CLSCorDataModel.ttl>
- CLSCor vocabularies: <https://gitlab.clsinfra.io/cls-infra/wp567/clscor/-/tree/main/vocabs>
- CLSCor catalogue: <https://clscor.io/>
- SARI project documentation: <https://docs.swissartresearch.net/>
- CLSCorGi: <https://github.com/lu-pl/clscorgi>
- ACDH-CH: <https://www.oeaw.ac.at/acdh/acdh-ch-home>
- Project Gutenberg: <https://www.gutenberg.org/>
- Notebooks for NER, relation extraction and sentiment analysis: <https://github.com/GhentCDH/CLSinfra>

10. Appendix

10.1 List of prefixes and namespaces

prefix	namespace / URI-schema	description
clscor	<https://clscor.io/entity/{hash-id}>	Dedicated CLSCor namespace for general, i.e., not corpus-specific instances
clst	<https://clscor.io/entity/type/{vocab-key}/{term-key}>	Dedicated CLSCor namespace for defining types
crm	<http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>	Basic CIDOC CRM ontology
crmcls	<https://clscor.io/ontologies/CRMcls/>	Main CLSCor ontology, extension of CIDOC CRM
crmdig	<http://www.ics.forth.gr/is1/CRMdig/>	CIDOC CRM compatible ontology to encode methods of production of digital objects
lrm	<http://iflastandards.info/ns/lrm/lrmoo/>	LRMoo (formerly FRBRoo); CIDOC CRM compatible ontology
owl	<http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>	Web Ontology Language
pem	<http://parthenos.d4science.org/CRMext/CRMpe.rdfs>	PARTHENOS Entities Model
rdf	<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>	Resource Description Framework
rdfs	<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>	Resource Description Framework Schema
skos	<http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>	Simple Knowledge Organisation System
xsd	<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>	Namespace for the XML schema